

Transfer Learning Model for Offline Handwritten Arabic Signature Recognition

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Abstract— The verification of handwritten signatures is a significant area of research in computer vision and machine learning (ML). Handwritten signatures serve as unique biometric identifiers, making it essential to distinguish between genuine and forged signatures. This binary classification task is crucial in legal and financial contexts to prevent fraud and protect customers from potential losses. However, verifying offline handwritten signatures is challenging due to variations in handwriting influenced by factors such as mood, fatigue, writing surface, and writing instrument. This research paper focuses on recognizing offline handwritten Arabic signatures using deep learning (DL), specifically transfer learning (TL) technique which is called “Inception-V3 TL model”. Three distinct datasets are used to build a model for recognizing signatures. The first dataset is referred to as Dataset1. It is an English signature dataset called “CEDAR” which contains 1,320 genuine and 1,320 forged signatures. Dataset1 is publicly available at: <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/shreelakshmigp/cedarataset>. The second dataset is referred to as Dataset2. It is a new Arabic signature dataset created for this research which contains 1,320 genuine and 1,320 forged signatures. The third dataset is referred to as Dataset3. It is created by merging the English and Arabic signature datasets (Dataset1 and Dataset2). The Inception-V3 TL model is trained on these distinct datasets (Dataset1, Dataset2, and Dataset3). Both normal training and k-fold cross-validation (CV) methods are applied to evaluate the model’s performance, ensuring robustness and reliability. The Inception-V3 model achieved impressive accuracies of 97.48% on the Dataset1, 98.23% on Dataset2, and 97.85% on Dataset3, demonstrating its effectiveness in distinguishing between genuine and forged signatures.

Keywords— *Handwritten Signatures, Offline Recognition, Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN), biometric, Transfer learning, Inception-V3 model.*

I. INTRODUCTION

A signature is defined as a unique, individual, and personal sign. It is regarded as one of the biometric measurements that can be used for identification and verification. Handwritten signatures have been used in different practical areas of life for many centuries, for example, in contracts, financial operations, documents, identification documents such as passports, driver’s licenses, etc. Additionally, signatures are used in bank cheques and money transfers. However, with the great benefits of using a handwritten signature, came certain challenges for societies such as identity and fraud [1].

Signatures can be broadly categorized into two types: offline and online. Offline signatures, which are normally penned on paper and then captured electronically using scanners or cameras, present significant difficulties in terms of authentication. These difficulties stem from handwriting changes due to mood, fatigue, and writing environment, reproduction and forgery. Other factors that influence the level of accuracy in verification include lighting and the quality of scanning. On the other hand, online signatures that are collected at the time of signing using digital devices like tablets or smartphones are richer in information such as speed of writing, pressure, and sequence of writing, making them more secure and easier to verify. Even today, the process of verifying the offline handwritten signatures is particularly difficult due to these complex factors [1]. Handwritten signature recognition appears as an essential field of study in the domain of pattern recognition and biometric identification. Due to the increased demand for security in the identification process, it is important to accurately identify and verify handwritten signatures.

Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) are identified as highly efficient models, which have reported remarkable performance in image classification problems. Their ability to harness TL suggests that signature recognition systems can be

improved in the future [2], especially when it comes to recognizing Arabic handwriting, which is quite challenging due to the complexity of the script [3].

CNNs are quite good at extracting features from raw pixel data since they are designed to operate with grid-like data, such as photographs. When there is a shortage of data in the dataset, TL is particularly useful. This method utilizes models that have already been trained for different purposes, improving the accuracy and generalization of the models while reducing computational costs and training time [4].

Arabic handwriting is complex due to its cursive writing style, variety of writing patterns, and diacritical markings, which creates particular difficulties [3].

CNNs are ideally equipped to handle these problems because of their hierarchical feature extraction capabilities. By using insights from large image recognition datasets, CNNs that use TL can further increase their performance in handwriting Arabic signature classification [4].

To sum up, there is a lot of potential in evaluating TL methods in CNN models for Arabic handwritten signature recognition. This research paper can help design more accurate and efficient signature verification systems by tackling the difficulties involved in handwritten signature verification. Such advancements have wide-ranging implications for sectors such as banking, legal, and governmental applications, where signature verification is critical.

II. Background

This section gives a brief background about signature recognition. Signature recognition is a technique used to determine whether a signature is genuine or forged. This process is referred to as offline handwritten signature verification. In this context, there are three types of signature forgery:

1. Random forgery: The forger creates the signature without knowing the name of the original signer.
2. Simple forgery: The forger attempts the forgery after knowing the name of the author but has no knowledge of the true signature.
3. Expert forgery: The forger executes the forgery when they have a sample of the true signature. This type of forgery has been addressed in this research paper. The close resemblance of a skilled forged signature to the original signature presents a significant challenge in signature verification. To address this challenge, the design of an effective signature verification system becomes imperative, where there is currently a need to process a person's identity faster and more accurately [5],[6].

As shown in Figure 1, adopted from Hashim et al. [5], the signature verification processes consist of the following steps [5]:

Fig.1. Signature recognition process.

- Data Acquisition: This is the essential first step in the signature verification process. In offline systems, data is collected using devices such as cameras or optical scanners to convert signature images into digital format. Researchers can also evaluate system performance using publicly available datasets from the Internet.
- Data Preprocessing: This step involves enhancing signature data and is crucial in signature verification systems. Image preprocessing entails several operations on signature images, including converting color images to grayscale, removing noise, applying thresholding and performing cropping.
- Feature Extraction: In this step, various features of the signature are extracted. These extracted features serve as the inputs for the training and recognition stages. Important features may include writing speed, pressure applied during signing, angle of the pen, curvature of the strokes, dimensions of the signature, and the style of writing. These characteristics play a crucial role in differentiating between genuine and forged signatures.
- Classification: It is a technique used to assess the validity of a given signature. Following the feature extraction stage, the extracted features are compared with those stored in a database. If the features match, the signature is classified as genuine; otherwise, it is considered forged. Neural networks (NN) and DL techniques are among the most commonly employed methods for classification .

III. Literature Review

Although Arabic is a widely spoken language, research in the field of Arabic signature recognition is limited compared to other human languages. In this section, we review previous research in the field of offline Arabic and English handwritten signature recognition. Most of the research focuses on providing suitable techniques for signature recognition and how to obtain good results using ML and DL algorithms.

A. Machine learning Techniques

The following previous studies are presented from the earliest to the latest ones:

Kruthi and Shet (2014) [7] have used a support vector machine (SVM) algorithm for identity verification of offline signatures based on the feature values in the database. The results indicated that the SVM algorithm was successfully tested against 336 signature samples, and the classification error rate was less than 7.16%, which is found to be convincing. It can be argued that the dataset used in this study was relatively small, which may limit the generalizability of the results. Also, the accuracy may be enhanced using DL techniques.

Abdelghani and Amara (2015) [8] have proposed a new approach for offline handwritten signature verification using a Planar Multi-Classifer Modeling (PMCM) architecture, combining NN and SVM. The study demonstrated promising results on two databases, SID-Signature and GPDS-160. It can be observed that the genuine signatures in SID-Signature database were in a different language than the simple forged signatures, which were predominantly in Arabic [9]. This inconsistency can complicate the verification process and may reduce the model's accuracy. Therefore, creation of an Arabic signature dataset could be beneficial, also the accuracy may be enhanced using DL techniques.

Based on the Back Propagation of ANN algorithm, Rahmi et al. (2016) [10] conducted a study to recognize a number of signatures in order to determine whether the recognition using Back Propagation is appropriate. The achieved accuracy of 63% is relatively low, indicating substantial room for improvement in the recognition process. Additionally, the study did not address the rotation of images, which may negatively impact the classification results. Expanding the dataset to include a larger and more diverse set of signatures may also contribute to improved recognition capabilities.

Darwish et al. (2016) [11] have proposed an algorithm for offline Arabic signature verification, utilizing multiple feature fusion combined with fuzzy modelling to enhance verification accuracy. Various classifiers were used, including SVM, K-Nearest Neighbours (KNN), NN, and fuzzy logic models, to improve the robustness of the verification process. The results indicated that the proposed system achieved an accuracy of 91%, demonstrating a reduction in both the False Acceptance Rate (FAR) and False Rejection Rate (FRR). Despite the high accuracy achieved, the study did not use DL techniques, which could enhance performance.

More techniques were used by Thenuwara and Nagahamulla (2017) [12] to find a feasible solution to verify handwritten signatures, including Multinomial Naive Bayes Classifier (MNBC), Logistic Regression Classifier (LRC), Stochastic Gradient Descent

Classifier (SGDC), Bernoulli Naive Bayes Classifier (BNBC), and Random Forest Classifier (RFC). The signature collection contains authentic signatures from 100 writers and forged signatures from 33 writers, totalling 1953 offline signature files. The RFC has achieved the best performance with an accuracy score of about 0.67. As a result, there is a need to expand the dataset to improve accuracy, also the model's performance could be enhanced using DL techniques.

Abdulhussain et al. (2023) [13] have proposed a genetic algorithm-based model for Arabic forgery signature verification using a one-class support vector machine (OCSVM-GA). Experimental results showed that the proposed model achieved lower FAR. It should be noted that, using DL techniques especially TL ones, may enhance feature extraction and overall robustness against signature variations.

Zhang et al. (2024) [14] have proposed an offline handwritten signature verification method utilizing a Variational Auto-encoder (VAE) to extract features directly from signature images. Traditional VAEs were enhanced by introducing a new loss function aimed at feature disentangling. For classification, Support Vector Machine (SVM) was employed based on the extracted features. Extensive experiments were conducted on two public datasets, MCYT-75 and GPDS-synthetic. Although the results achieved were promising, incorporating other DL techniques, such as CNNs, could potentially enhance performance further and improve the model's robustness in verifying signature.

B. Deep learning Techniques

The following previous studies are presented from the earliest to the latest ones:

In contrast to the studies mentioned above, Pokharel et al. (2020) [15] used the CNNs based on the Google Net architecture as a DL model. TL technique was applied, where the classification layer was retrained using a training dataset, and the model was evaluated using a test dataset. The model achieved an accuracy of 95.2%. However, it is worth noting that the authors opted to use the original GoogleNet architecture, despite the availability of more advanced versions such as Inceptionv2 and Inceptionv3, which could potentially enhance performance and efficiency.

Lopes et al. (2022) [16] conducted a study to verify offline handwritten signature using Deep Neural Networks (DNNs). Optical Mark Recognition (OMR) was used to detect the presence of signatures, also a multiclass CNN inspired by the AlexNet architecture is used to classify genuine and forged signatures. In our opinion, it could be beneficial to apply multiple models of TL that may improve the overall performance of the signature verification system.

Hung et al. (2023) [17] utilized a Siamese Triplet CNN architecture combined with a fully-connected NN to automatically verify genuine and forged signatures,

also the Xception model was employed to enhance the effectiveness of the verification model. The proposed model achieved an Equal Error Rate (EER) of 14.18% on the BHSig260 public dataset. However, it would be beneficial to test the model on multiple datasets to provide a more comprehensive evaluation of the model's performance and generalizability across different signature styles and conditions.

Ebrahimipour (2023) [18] proposed handwritten signature forgery detection using pre-trained DL methods such as MobileNet, ResNet, DenseNet, and EfficientNet to effectively detect forged signatures. Although an accuracy of 98.44% was achieved, it could be beneficial to use an additional dataset in a different language to enhance the model's reliability and generalizability across diverse applications.

In a recent study conducted by AlKarem et al. (2024) [19], regarding signature verification using CNNs to enhance verification accuracy, the model was trained on an English signature dataset and evaluated using a new Arabic signature dataset, achieving an accuracy of 95.36%. Despite achieving good results, improving accuracy may require more training data, especially with the diversity of signatures, and TL could be used to enhance the performance.

Finally, Abdirahma et al. (2024) [20] conducted a comprehensive analysis of handwritten signature verification using DL techniques. a MobileNet was used for extracting essential features, and Inceptionv3, VGG-19, and ResNet50 were used for signature classification by aggregating the strengths of each individual model. Although the models were applied on four datasets: Kaggle Signature, CEDAR, ICDAR, and Sigcomp, it would be beneficial to combine at least two of these datasets, especially if included different languages are included which may enhance the models' reliability and robustness.

IV. DATA PREPARATION

This section describes the datasets used to train and test the Inception-V3 model, including data preprocessing techniques which are applied to enhance the quality and usability of the data, as well as the data splitting strategy used.

A. Data Collection

An English signature dataset called "CEDAR" is adopted, which consists of 55 writers with 24 genuine signatures per writer, thus creating 1,320 original signatures. To obtain forged signatures, some were asked to forge other writers' signatures, thus creating 1,320 forgeries. The CEDAR dataset is a public dataset available to the public at:

<https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/shreelakshmi/gp/cedar-dataset>. Throughout the paper, this dataset is referred to as Dataset1. Figure 2 shows an example of an

original signature and a forged signature from the Dataset1.

Fig.2.A sample from Dataset1: a) original b) Forgery Signature

Additionally, a new dataset of Arabic signatures was created. A special signature collection form was distributed to a sample of approximately 150 individuals with official signatures used in banks. Data were collected for each writer in six sessions held on different days. A total of 95 forms were recovered, of which 40 were not valid. Each of the 55 individuals contributed 24 signatures, thus creating 1,320 original signatures. Throughout the paper, this dataset is referred to as Dataset2. For each writer, three forgers were instructed to create 8 copies of the writer's signature, resulting in 24 forgeries for each signature, thus creating 1,320 forged signatures. Each form was cut into 24 pieces. Each signature was scanned at 300 dots per inch (dpi) in grayscale. Figure 3 shows an exemplar of an original signature and a forged one from Dataset2.

Fig.3. A sample from Dataset2: a) original b) Forgery Signature

Furthermore, a third dataset was created by merging the English and Arabic signature datasets. This combined dataset includes a total of 2,640 original signatures and 2,640 forged signatures, providing a more extensive resource for analysis and research. Throughout the paper, this dataset is referred to as Dataset3.

B. Preprocessing

Preprocessing is done to improve the image quality so that it can be efficiently applied to the feature extraction stage. Images may contain blurry pixels and complex backgrounds, which pose challenges for offline signature verification systems. Therefore,

various preprocessing techniques were applied to create an enhanced image suitable for signature recognition. Standard preprocessing steps include: extracting the signature from the entire image and removing the background. Salt-and-pepper noise removal was also an important step involved in image preprocessing. Additionally, the image was converted to binary using a grayscale histogram, applying Otsu's method for optimal threshold selection.

C. Data Splitting

Data splitting is a crucial step in preparing datasets for ML models. Initially, the datasets are divided into three parts: 70% for training, 15% for validation, and 15% for testing. This structure ensures effective model evaluation and helps prevent overfitting, which occurs when a model performs exceptionally well on the training dataset but fails to generalize to validation data. In addition to this initial split, a CV method is employed, specifically using 10-fold CV. In this method, the training set (70% of the total data) is further divided into training and validation subsets. Typically, a common approach is to divide the training data into 90% for training and 10% for validation within each fold. This allows for robust validation during the training process while keeping 30% of the entire dataset reserved for final testing, ensuring that the model is fine-tuned on multiple subsets of the data before evaluation.

D. Data Augmentation and Normalization

Data augmentation and normalization play a critical role in enhancing the training and validation datasets. This process is executed using the ImageDataGenerator class. For the training data, various transformations are applied, including rescaling pixel values to a range of [0, 1]. Additionally, random shear transformations with a shear range of 0.2, zoom augmentations with a zoom range of 0.2, and horizontal flip augmentations are utilized. These augmentations significantly enhance the diversity of the training dataset, allowing the model to generalize better to unseen data.

For the validation dataset, only pixel normalization is performed to ensure consistency in the input data. The images are loaded from their respective directories, resized to the specified dimensions of (IMAGE_WIDTH, IMAGE_HEIGHT), and organized into batches of 32 for efficient processing during model training. This augmentation and normalization process is crucial for improving the performance and robustness of the signature recognition model, making it a fundamental aspect of the overall data preparation strategy.

V. MODEL BUILDING

In this section, the key components of the Inception-v3 model adopted for offline handwritten signature recognition are discussed, including the techniques employed for feature extraction that enhance the model's performance.

A. Inception-v3 Architecture

The Inception-v3 architecture is a DNN model developed by Google, introduced in 2015, aimed at improving classification accuracy while reducing computational complexity. This architecture enhances performance and efficiency in image processing through a complex set of layers. As shown in figure 4, adopted from Ali et al. [21], the Inception-V3 consists of several key components suitable for TL applications [21], as follows:

1. **Input Layer:** The dimensions are typically (299, 299, 3), suitable for processing color images.
2. **Inception Modules:** The architecture includes multiple interleaved Inception modules that combine convolutions of different sizes (1x1, 3x3, and 5x5) within the same layer, allowing the model to capture a variety of features from the input data. This design contributes to the model's high classification accuracy, making it particularly effective in tasks such as image recognition.
3. **Deep Convolutions:** Inception-v3 employs multiple convolutional layers to enhance feature extraction, facilitating robust learning of complex patterns. The model's structure minimizes information loss during the learning process, further improving overall performance.
4. **Pooling Layers:** The model utilizes max pooling and average pooling layers to reduce the dimensionality of the data while maintaining essential features, thereby enhancing efficiency in resource utilization. This efficiency makes Inception-V3 suitable for deployment in resource-limited environments, such as mobile devices.
5. **Fully Connected Layers:** Fully connected layers are included at the end of the architecture for classifying the extracted features, typically utilizing a SoftMax function for output.
6. **Normalization:** Batch normalization is commonly applied to the inputs of the activation layers to stabilize and improve the learning process. This technique contributes to faster training speeds and higher accuracy.
7. **Dropout:** Dropout layers are integrated to reduce overfitting, enhancing the model's ability to generalize to new data and ensuring its adaptability to various types of tasks.

Overall, Inception-V3's architecture combines these elements to achieve high classification accuracy, efficient resource utilization, and flexibility in a wide range of computer vision applications, establishing it as one of the leading models in DL [22].

Fig.4. The Inception-V3 model architecture.

B. Feature Extraction

Extracting meaningful features from images is crucial for signature recognition. In this research paper, pre-trained CNNs models were utilized for this purpose.

- Loading pre-trained CNNs Models:

These models were initialized with weights pre-trained on the ImageNet dataset, excluding the final classification layers to adapt them for feature extraction.

- Freezing the Layers:

All layers were frozen to retain the learned features, preventing weight updates during training. This step ensures that the models provide robust feature representations relevant to signature recognition.

- Feature Extraction Process:

Signature images were processed through the pre-trained model to obtain feature maps, which serve as inputs for the subsequent classification model.

- Utilizing Extracted Features:

The extracted features are processed through dense layers in a custom model, ultimately predicting whether a signature is genuine or forged.

In summary, using pre-trained model for feature extraction enhances the performance of the signature recognition system. Figure 5, adopted from Khan et al. [23], illustrates the feature extraction process.

Fig.5. The process of feature extraction via TL.

VI. MODEL'S RESULTS AND PERFORMANCE

This section presents and discusses the results obtained from training the Inception-V3 model using three different datasets, namely Dataset1, Dataset2, and Dataset3. The training was conducted using two methods: normal training and cross-validation. Additionally, well-known evaluation metrics, as well as those specifically used to assess the adopted model, are discussed.

A. Normal Training Method

Evaluating the performance of the Inception-V3 model using three different datasets has revealed that the model achieved impressive accuracies of 97.48%, 98.23% and 97.85% for Dataset1, Dataset2, and Dataset3, respectively. Figure 6 shows a graph which illustrates the training loss and validation loss during the training process for Dataset 2 (Arabic Dataset).

Fig.6. A graph of training and validation loss for Dataset2.

In addition to the insights gained from the training and validation loss curves, the model's classification performance was further evaluated using a detailed report. Figure 8 presents the classification report for Dataset 2.

Classification Report:				
	precision	recall	f1-score	support
0	0.989744	0.974747	0.982188	198
1	0.975124	0.989899	0.982456	198
accuracy			0.982323	396
macro avg	0.982434	0.982323	0.982322	396
weighted avg	0.982434	0.982323	0.982322	396

Fig.7. The classification report for Dataset 2.

B. Cross-Validation Method

In this stage, the robustness of the models will be enhanced by employing a CV approach. Unlike the first stage, where the dataset was split into training, validation, and test sets, CV allows for more efficient utilization of the data by systematically rotating through different subsets for training and validation. Using the 10-fold CV method with the Inception-V3 model achieved impressive accuracies of 98.86% and 94.96% for Dataset1 and Dataset2, respectively. This high accuracy emphasizes the model's ability to effectively recognize signatures. In addition, Figure 8 presents a plot illustrating the training loss and validation loss during the training process for Dataset2 (Arabic Dataset).

Fig.8. A graph of training and validation loss for Dataset2

Furthermore, a classification report for Dataset2 will be presented, providing detailed insights into the model's performance across various metrics, such as precision, recall, and F1-score. This report will help assess the effectiveness of the model in distinguishing between genuine and forged signatures. Figure 9 illustrates this classification report.

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Classification Report for Test Dataset:
      precision    recall  f1-score   support

     0       0.963636    0.934509    0.948849       397
     1       0.936430    0.964736    0.950372       397

 accuracy          0.949622         794
 macro avg       0.950033    0.949622    0.949611         794
 weighted avg    0.950033    0.949622    0.949611         794
    
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Fig.9. The classification report for dataset 2

Overall, the model performs well across all datasets, achieving the highest accuracy on Dataset1 with CV. The use of CV helped reduce overfitting, indicating its crucial role in enhancing the model's generalizability and robustness.

VII. SUMMARY OF THE RESULTS

The results obtained from the experiments are summarized as given in Table I. Key findings from the analysis highlight the effectiveness of the Inception-V3 DL model applied to three datasets: Dataset1, Dataset2,

and Dataset3. The accuracy metric is included to provide a clear overview of model's performance, facilitating an easy comparison between the datasets. Additionally, a sample of predictions on unseen signatures are presented as shown in Figure 10, displaying each signature image alongside its label (genuine or forged) and the model's prediction. This sample of predictions emphasizes the effectiveness of the Inception-V3 model for signature recognition task.

Table I: SUMMARY OF THE RESULTS FOR THE INCEPTION-V3 MODEL USING THREE DIFFERENT DATASETS.

Validation Method	Model	Dataset	Validation Loss	Training Loss	Accuracy
Normal Training	Inception-V3	Dataset1	0.0216	0.0461	97.48%
		Dataset2	0.0196	0.0780	98.23%
		Dataset3	0.0544	0.0269	97.85%
Cross-validation	Inception-V3	Dataset1	0.0328	0.0555	98.86%
		Dataset2	0.1391	0.1354	94.96%

Fig.10. Signature Prediction Examples

As shown in Table I, it can be observed that the results of Dataset3 are similar with the results of both Dataset1 and dataset2, which indicates that TL model is not being influenced by data augmentation.

Based on the results shown in Table I; although all the results are satisfactory and encouraging, it can be noticed that the Inception-V3 model achieved high accuracy rates on dataset2 using normal training and CV methods. In comparison with previous studies which used Arabic signature datasets, it is obvious that our results are higher than those obtained by Abdulghani and Amara 2015 [8] where the study achieved 91% of accuracy, Darwish et al. 2016 [11] where the proposed system also achieved an accuracy of 91%, and AlKarem et al. 2024 [21] where the proposed model achieved an accuracy of 95.36%.

VIII. CONCLUSION

This research study has examined the extent of effectiveness of DL techniques in terms of various feature extraction for signature recognition. This may play a crucial role in ensuring the security and integrity of sensitive documents and transactions moving forward. It can be concluded that TL models have shown great promise in accurately identifying genuine signatures while minimizing false positives.

In this research, a new dataset (Dataset2) of offline handwritten Arabic signatures was created consisting of 1320 genuine and 1320 forged signatures. Three different datasets, namely: Dataset1, Dataset2, and Dataset3 are used to train the Inception-V3 TL model.

For distinguishing between genuine and forged signatures using normal training, the performance of the Inception-V3 TL model has shown that high accuracies of about (97.48%, 98.23%, and 97.85%) are achieved on Dataset1, Dataset2, and Dataset3 respectively. On the other hand, and using CV method, the performance of the Inception-V3 TL model has achieved accuracies of about (98.86% and 94.96%,) on Dataset1 and Dataset2 respectively.

IX. FUTURE WORK

Given the results demonstrated earlier, some ideas can be suggested that may be topics for future studies to enhance signature recognition systems.

Future research can be extended to include development of models for online Arabic signature recognition, which enhances broader applications in digital environments.

In addition, further research is needed to shed light on the investigation of the signatures of left-handed individuals, particularly in scenarios where forgers use their right hand, which will provide insights into distinguishing authentic signatures from forgeries.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

First and foremost, we praise and thank Allah for enabling us to complete this research study. Additionally, we extend our appreciation to those who generously provided their handwritten signatures to create a dataset for this work, as their contributions were invaluable.

We would like to express our gratitude and appreciation to Libyan Academy and Libyan Ministry of Higher Education & Scientific Research for the logistic support.

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